

EXPERIMENTS ON JOINTS COMPOSED OF PULTRUDED GFRP TUBES BONDED TO GFRP LAMELLAS

Z. Rybchenko, J. B. Deroyer-Dupré, L. Mistiaen, T. Vallée*
Laboratory of Timber and Composites
Berne University of Applied Sciences, CH-2504 Biel, Switzerland
* till.vallee@bfh.ch

SUMMARY

Adhesive bonding represents the most material-adapted and efficient method for joining pultruded glass fibre-reinforced (GFRP) components. Up to know, research has concentrated on relatively simple single and double lap joints. This research presents experimental results and numerical investigations on joints composed of pultruded GFRP tubes bonded to GFRP lamellas.

Keywords: Adhesive, bonded, joints composites, experimental, FEA

INTRODUCTION

Considering the fibrous and anisotropic nature of composite materials, it is obvious that adhesively bonded joints represent the most adapted method to connect such elements. Research on adhesively bonded connections has focused on the investigation of relatively simple systems, like single and double-lap joints.

An extensive literature review by da Silva et al. on existing analytical models has been published recently for simple lap joints, either single or double [1]. It was shown that almost all analytical models for adhesively bonded lap joints are two-dimensional. Because the stresses in the width direction are significantly lower than in the direction of the loading, this is generally considered sufficient. Similarly, almost all analyses are for linear elastic material behavior, for both adherends and adhesive; including non-linearity, i.e. plasticity, would make the solution too complex for analytical approaches. The same authors concluded in [2], regarding analytical solutions, that “*the implementation and resolution of nonlinear analyses is time consuming and the advantage in relationship to a finite-element analysis is questionable*”, clearly indicating that FEA is a by far better tool for the analysis of bonded joints.

Regarding experimental investigations, Keller and Vallée [3] carried out axial traction tests on adhesively bonded joints composed of pultruded GFRP adherends using a brittle and linear elastic epoxy adhesive. They pointed out the main characteristics related to their failure mode, which was reported to be brittle after an almost linear-elastic mechanical response. Failure, in the particular case of pultruded GFRP, was usually triggered inside the composite. A closer look at the failure locus showed that, due to the specificities of pultruded GFRP in which mats of fleece layers wraps up a threads of axial glass fibres (called rovings), failure occurred at a certain depth, $t_f =$

0.5...1.5 mm, inside the material; it was shown that this location corresponds to a resin rich layer separating the fleece from the rovings. For a better understanding of the latter, the reader is kindly referred to Fig. 1.

The investigations reported in [3] also showed a good to very good agreement between experimentally gathered and numerically computed strains under the bonded splice, which allowed concluding that FEA is a suitable tool to describe the stress-strain state inside adhesively bonded joints, if the mechanical parameters are known. The numerical modelling of the joints clearly indicated that failure is usually triggered by a combination of through-thickness, σ_y , shear τ_{xy} , and axial stresses, σ_x , at the joint edges in the adhesive fillet and/or in the layer of the outer fibre-mats. The experimentally observed failure initiation locus corresponded to the locations where these stresses, combined in a failure criterion, exhibited their maxima. Besides this, the numerical and experimental results showed that the adhesive layer thickness had only a small influence on the stress distributions within the thickness range of 1–3 mm.

Lastly, regarding the experiments described above, tests on similar joints (same GFRP) but joined using a much softer Polyurethane adhesive, which clearly exhibited a plastic behaviour were reported in [4]. It turned out that for otherwise identical conditions (i.e. geometry, material, loading rate etc.), the use of a “plastic” adhesive (Polyurethane) did not significantly affect the ultimate strength of the joints, although significant reductions in the stress magnitudes were numerically determined.

Fig. 1 – Cross section of the investigated GFRP material showing the mats and the rovings

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

To extend the range of investigated adhesively bonded joints, and in response to a need formulated by practitioners, the authors performed experimental investigations on a joint type that radically differs from the usually considered lap joints: a joint consisting in hollow cylindrical pultruded GFRP tubes connected through a bracket to flat pultruded profiles. This type of joint is encountered in situations like strut-and-tie structures, where it is more advantageous to increase the buckling load of ties in compression, thus choosing a tubular section. Figure 3 and 4 depict the investigated joints.

Pultruded GFRP profiles with flat rectangular sections were used in the experimental part of the project described herein. The material consisted of E-glass fibres embedded in an isophthalic polyester resin. Contrary to traditional laminated materials, the fibre architecture comprised mainly unidirectional rovings towards the centre and, depending on the profile thickness, one or two combined mats towards the outside, as shown in Fig. 1 for a 10 mm thick profile. The combined mats consisted of chopped strand mats (CSM) as well as woven mats $0^\circ/90^\circ$ of different weights, both stitched together. Furthermore, a protective polyester surface veil (40 g/m^2) covered the outsides.

The joints investigated herein consisted of GFRP tubes ($\text{Ø}40\text{mm}$, $t=3\text{mm}$, $E_x=34.4\pm 0.6 \text{ GPa}$) connected through aluminium ($E=70'000 \text{ MPa}$) brackets to a GFRP flat profile ($t=10\text{mm}$, $E_x=32.5\pm 1.3 \text{ GPa}$) in which a space was cut. In all cases, the tube and the flat profile overlapped by $L=100 \text{ mm}$. All mechanical parameters of the GFRP, regarding stiffness and strength, were gathered on full scale lamellas equipped with strain gauges.

Adhesion was achieved by means of two different adhesives: a brittle 2C-Epoxy (SikaDur330: $E=4550 \text{ MPa}$, $f_t=38.1 \text{ MPa}$) and a soft 2C-Polyurethane (SikaForce7851: $E_{\text{elastic}}=586 \text{ MPa}$ up to $f_{\text{elastic}}=15 \text{ MPa}$, then $E_{\text{plastic}}=31 \text{ MPa}$, see also Fig. 2). The thickness of the adhesive layer, $t_a=1 \text{ mm}$, was achieved by means of calibrated spacers. Tension tests were performed according to ISO 527 while compression tests were performed using ASTM 695.

Prior to bonding, all surface were adequately cleaned and degreased, the adhesives were fully cured at room temperature.

Figure 2 – Experimental characterization of the adhesives;
(left) Epoxy σ - ϵ -curve, (right) Polyurethane σ - ϵ -curve

The through-thickness, f_y , shear f_{xy} , and axial strengths, f_x , were experimentally gathered on over 200 individual test coupons, involving different combinations of simultaneously acting stresses σ_y , τ_{xy} , and σ_x . It was found that $f_y=9.36$ MPa, $f_{xy}=22.56$ MPa and $f_x=434.0$ MPa. The reader is kindly asked to refer to [3–5] for more details regarding the mechanical properties of the GFRP and [6] for statistical distributions that describe the probability of survival of the investigated material.

All tests were performed using a universal testing machine with a capacity of 250 kN under quasi-static axial tension at a constant rate of loading of 0.5 mm/min.

Failure always, for both adhesives, occurred in a brittle manner, and was triggered in the tube, as shown in Fig. 2, at a depth of around 0.5 mm inside the GFRP, and never in the adhesive.

The experimentally determined strengths are (average \pm standard deviation):

- 66.17 \pm 1.00 kN for the Epoxy bonded joints
- 82.30 \pm 1.87 kN for the Polyurethane bonded ones

Figure 3 – Typical failure modes;
(left) Epoxy bonded joints, (right) Polyurethane bonded joints

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATIONS

The experimentally investigated adhesively bonded joints were modeled using the finite element program ANSYS (v11) using 8-node orthotropic elements, SOLID45. As the considered system exhibits two axis of symmetry, only one quarter was modeled.

The adhesive layers were subdivided into three or more layers. A mesh refinement was performed at the ends of the overlaps where the stresses increased asymptotically.

The GFRP adherends were modeled with linear-elastic and orthotropic material properties. The axial elastic moduli listed above were used to model the tube and the flat profile, while the through-thickness elastic properties for both were assumed to $E_z=3500$ MPa, according to [4].

The epoxy adhesive was modeled linear-elastic and isotropic; the elastic properties are listed above while the polyurethane was modeled as isotropic, with an idealized bilinear σ - ϵ -relationship according to Fig. 2.

The numerical calculation exhibited a similar pattern to what was already known for lap joints, the stresses in the bonded area tend to concentrate around the ends of the overlaps. In the case investigated herein, the non-linear mechanical response of the polyurethane lead to significant plastic strain in the corresponding numerical model, which in turn, at a load corresponding to the experimentally observed failure, corresponded to a stress reduction of around 41%, respectively to the epoxy bonded (which was almost linear-elastic)

Figure 4 – Contour plots obtained through numerical simulation; (left) axial displacements, (right) principal strains.

STRESS-BASED STRENGTH PREDICTION

In a stress-based context, strength should be predictable using a simple verification. To achieve such verification, a material failure criterion for the failing material must be considered. For the purpose of this study a Tsai-Hill formulation, given by Eqs. 1 has been used for the GFRP.

$$\frac{\sigma_1^2}{f_1^2} - \frac{\sigma_1\sigma_2}{f_1f_2} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{f_2^2} + \frac{\tau_{12}^2}{f_{12}^2} = 1$$

$$\frac{\sigma_1^2}{f_1^2} = 1 \quad \frac{\sigma_2^2}{f_2^2} = 1$$

(Eqs. 1)

Where σ_1 , σ_2 and τ_{12} are the stresses acting in the axial, through-thickness directions and shear stresses, respectively; f_1 , f_2 , and f_{12} the corresponding strengths, which have been previously determined (i.e. the axial strength, f_x , through-thickness, f_y , and shear f_{xy} strength). The joint's strengths according to a stress based approach, i.e. dimensioning the joint according to the highest stress combination, σ_F according to (Eq. 1), encountered in the FE model were also determined:

- 27.72 kN for the Epoxy bonded and
- 47.23 kN for the Polyurethane bonded.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Experimental and numerical investigations have been carried out to investigate experiments on joints composed of pultruded GFRP tubes bonded to GFRP lamellas, a kind of joint that clearly diverges from the usual lap joints investigated in literature.

Two different types of adhesives were used: a relatively brittle epoxy that did not exhibit any plasticity, and relatively soft polyurethane, clearly showing plastic behavior at higher stresses.

The experimental investigations showed just a substantial influence of the mechanical characteristics of the considered adhesive, i.e. the plastic behavior of the polyurethane did only allow for an increase of around 24% in terms of ultimate strengths. This partially contradicts similar results on adhesively bonded single and double lap joints of similar material.

The numerical modeling showed that huge stress concentrations arise at the end of the overlaps, similarly to what occurs for single and double lap joints. The location of the maximum in the numerical model corresponds to the experimentally observed locus of failure initiation. In no case did the adhesive fail; failure always initiated inside the GFRP, at a depth that corresponds to a resin-rich layer that separates the fleece-mats from the rovings.

Failure is triggered by a combination of through-thickness, σ_y , shear τ_{xy} , and axial stresses, σ_x , at the joint edges in the adhesive fillet and/or in the layer of the outer fibre-mats.

If considering a stress based approach for the strength determination, i.e. taking the single most stressed element, strength is underestimated, by 58% for the Epoxy bonded specimens and by 43% for the Polyurethane ones, clearly showing that a stress based approach is not suitable to correctly handle the issue of the huge stress peaks generated at the end of the overlap. This confirms previous results obtained on single and double lap joints by on of the authors, also on similar material.

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